

THE ROLE OF THE NATIVE LANGUAGE SUBJECT IN DEVELOPING THE SPEECH OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the role of the native language subject in the development of oral and written speech of primary school students from scientific-theoretical and practical perspectives. Through native language lessons, the possibilities of forming correct pronunciation, a rich vocabulary, grammatically correct and logically consistent speech in students are highlighted. Also, the types of exercises used in the process of speech development, the effectiveness of interactive methods and linguodidactic approaches are substantiated. The article concludes that the subject of the native language at the stage of primary education is an important pedagogical factor in the development of students' thinking abilities, communicative competence, and speech culture

Introduction.

One of the urgent tasks facing the education system today is the development of students' speech activity, the formation of their ability to express their thoughts fluently, logically, and in accordance with the norms of the literary language in oral and written form. Especially, the primary education stage is an important period in which students' speech, thinking, and communicative potential are formed. Therefore, at this stage, the issue of speech development through effective teaching of the native language acquires special pedagogical significance.

For elementary school students, the subject of the native language is not only a means of forming literacy, but also one of the main subjects that develops their speech culture, vocabulary, grammatical thinking, and independent thinking. In the process of native language lessons, students acquire skills in distinguishing sounds and letters, correctly constructing words and sentences, understanding the content of the text, and consistently expressing their thoughts. This process is carried out in close connection with speech development.

At the same time, the issue of speech development in modern education should not be limited to theoretical knowledge, but should be organized through practical exercises, interactive methods, and communicative approaches. In native language lessons, it is possible to increase the speech activity of students through various types of exercises, working with

texts, questions and answers, and creative tasks. This ensures their activity in the educational process and the effectiveness of assimilation.

This article scientifically illuminates the role of the native language in the development of speech in primary school students, the pedagogical significance of this process, and the effective methods and techniques used in speech development.

Methodology

The methodology of this study is aimed at identifying the didactic possibilities of the subject of the native language in the development of speech of primary school students and analyzing the effectiveness of this process on a scientific basis. In the research process, a complex system of methods was used, based on modern approaches to pedagogy, psychology, and linguodidactics.

The main place in the study was occupied by the method of theoretical analysis, in which scientific literature, regulatory legal acts, and current curricula on speech development, language competence, communicative approach, and primary education were studied. Through these analyses, existing approaches to speech development in native language lessons were summarized and their pedagogical significance was determined.

Observation, interviews, and diagnostic methods were used in the practical research process. In particular, through direct observation of native language lessons in primary grades, changes in students' oral and written speech, vocabulary, and the level of expression of thoughts were analyzed. Through conversations with teachers, the effectiveness of the methods and exercises used in speech development was determined.

Also, within the framework of the experimental work, a system of exercises aimed at speech development was developed and implemented in practice. These exercises were organized in phonetic, lexical, and grammatical directions, taking into account the age and psychological characteristics of the students. The results of the experiment were analyzed based on the methods of comparison and generalization, and the effectiveness of the native language in speech development was determined.

In order to ensure reliable and well-founded conclusions based on the results obtained in the study, a systematic approach and methods of pedagogical analysis were used. As a result, the methodological possibilities of the subject of the native language in the development of speech of primary school students were scientifically substantiated.

Results and discussion

The results of observations, interviews, and experimental work conducted during the research process confirmed that the subject of the native language is an important pedagogical tool in the development of speech of primary school students. In the experimental process, significant positive changes were observed in the oral and written speech of students in classes where a system of exercises aimed at speech development was used.

In particular, it was found that the vocabulary of students has expanded, the skill of appropriate use of words has been formed, and the level of grammatically correct sentence construction has increased. Through working with texts, questions and answers, storytelling, and creative writing, students developed the ability to consistently and logically express their thoughts. This served to improve the content and form of speech.

In the process of analyzing the results of the experimental work, it was established that the use of interactive methods and communicative approaches in native language lessons significantly increases the speech activity of students. During the lesson, students strived to freely express their opinions, participate in discussions, and draw independent conclusions. As a result, speech was formed not only as a means of expressing knowledge, but also as a factor in the development of thinking.

The results obtained during the discussion were compared with existing pedagogical research. Comparisons have shown that limiting oneself to traditional exercises in speech development does not yield the expected results. On the contrary, high results can be achieved by combining linguistic knowledge with practical speech activity, involving students in active communication. This situation further strengthens the communicative and developmental function of the science of the native language.

Also, the research results showed the need to increase the proportion of exercises aimed at speech development when planning native language lessons in primary education, to choose methods taking into account the age and individual characteristics of students. This approach allows for the consistent development of students' speech culture and communicative competence.

In general, the obtained results scientifically substantiated the decisive role of the subject of the native language in the development of speech of primary school students and showed the need to improve methodological work carried out within the framework of this subject.

Conclusion

The research results showed that the subject of the native language is of leading and decisive pedagogical significance in the process of developing the speech of primary school students. It has been scientifically proven that through native language lessons, students have the opportunity to form the main structural elements of oral and written speech - correct pronunciation, a rich vocabulary, grammatically correct and logically consistent speech.

According to the results of the experimental work, the consistent implementation of a system of exercises aimed at speech development, interactive methods, and communicative approaches in native language lessons increases the speech activity of students, develops independent thinking and the ability to freely express one's opinion. This serves as an important factor in the formation of speech culture and communicative competence at the stage of primary education.

Also, the research results showed the need for a systematic and targeted approach to the issue of speech development in teaching the subject of native language. The selection of exercises and tasks, taking into account the age and psychological characteristics of students, the combination of theoretical knowledge with practical speech activity ensures high efficiency.

In general, the subject of the native language manifests itself as an important subject that has not only educational, but also developmental and educational significance in the development of speech of primary school students. The results of this study serve as a scientific and methodological basis for the further improvement of native language lessons in

primary education and the widespread introduction into practice of methodological approaches aimed at speech development.

List of literature:

1. Asqarova, M., va boshqalar. "Kichik yoshdagi bolalar nutqini o'stirish". -Toshkent: "O'qituvchi". 2001.
2. Gulomov, A., Qobilova, B. "Nutq o'stirish mashg'ulotlari". -Toshkent: "O'qituvchi". 1995)
3. Javohir G'aybullo o'g, Z. (2025). The Importance of Effective Use of Exercise Types in Primary Education Mother Tongue Lessons. *International Journal of Diversity and Multiculturalism*, 2(1), 63-67.
4. Javohir G'aybullo o'g, Z. (2025). Ona tili darslarida asos va qo'shimchalarni o'rgatishda turli xil metodlardan foydalanishning o'rni. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 38(3), 401-406.
5. Matchonov, S. "Ona tili va o'qish savodxonligi metodikasi" (Darslik). Toshkent: "Innovatsiyo ziyo". 2022
6. ugli, Z. J. G. (2023). Classification of Educational Tasks From the Mother Language. *Journal of Higher Education and Academic Advancement*, 1(1), 111-116. <https://doi.org/10.61796/ejheaa.v1i1.47>
7. ugli, Z. J. G. (2023). Effectiveness of Using the Cognitive-Pragmatic Method in Primary-Grade Mother Language Education. *Journal of Higher Education and Academic Advancement*, 1(1), 63-66. <https://doi.org/10.61796/ejheaa.v1i1.39>
8. ugli, Z. J. G. (2023). The Problem of Designing Students' Creative Activities by Means of Pragmatic Exercises in Mother Language Education. *Journal of Higher Education and Academic Advancement*, 1(1), 105-110. <https://doi.org/10.61796/ejheaa.v1i1.46>
9. ugli, Z. J. G. . (2023). A Concept of Upgrading the Content of Mother Language Education. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 6(7), 8-12. <https://doi.org/10.31149/ijie.v6i7.4576>